

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING (PjBL) MODEL IMPROVES THE CREATIVITY OF VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL (SMK) STUDENTS IN THE INFORMATICS PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT: *In the era of modern education in the 21st century, students really need to be trained to have strong creativity, not only in the arts, but also in various professions or fields such as informatics. Vocational High Schools (SMK), especially the informatics department, have great advantages in shaping students to be work-ready through hands-on practice, although traditional teaching methods often do not encourage their imagination. From various previous studies, it can be seen that project-based learning or Project Based Learning (PjBL) is very effective as a solution to stimulate students' creativity, with successful examples from Asian countries such as Singapore, which has advanced in its curriculum. The literature review also concludes that PjBL is very suitable for SMK, especially informatics, because students can learn while working on real tasks or practical work that can train and develop creativity and problem-solving, in accordance with the demands of today's digital world. This study uses a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach to collect data, focusing on articles from 1997 to 2025 searched through Google Scholar using keywords such as Project Based Learning and Critical Thinking, as well as the creativity of important points from these studies, ensuring the process is systematic and objective. The main findings show that PjBL truly increases students' creativity through steps such as identifying problems, planning projects, and reflecting on results, which ultimately trains critical thinking skills and teamwork. In the discussion, this method is proven to be superior for improving students' critical thinking compared to classical teaching because it makes students more active and motivated, with positive impacts on their learning scores and career preparation. Overall, this review encourages vocational informatics schools to apply PjBL more frequently so their graduates can be more innovative and competitive amid rapid technological development.*

Keywords: **PjBL, Informatics, Creative, Critical, Thinking.**

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, education requires students to master various skills that are relevant to the development of the times, and one of the many abilities that is increasingly considered important is creativity. This ability is no longer limited to the field of arts, but also needed in various fields of knowledge and professions. Therefore, all educational institutions are required to choose learning methods that are able to foster and improve the creativity of students (Telaumbanua et al., 2025). In a learning process, education plays a very large role in shaping students' creativity and students being able to think critically as one of the many important aspects

to support learning success(Maro, 2016). One approach to fostering student creativity that has received much attention is the project-based learning method. This learning method emphasizes active and collaborative learning activities and provides plenty of space for students to explore ideas independently. Through projects designed and carried out by students, this method is expected to foster or increase creativity, encourage innovation, and train problem-solving skills(Dewi et al., 2022). Because education has a major role in shaping the creativity of students, which is one of the important elements in the learning process, project-based learning methods are increasingly being chosen in educational practices(Flack & Meador, 1997).

The success of education in Indonesia is still not comparable to the achievements of Asian countries that have excellent education systems. Although Indonesia has carried out several curriculum reforms, the structure and quality of the national curriculum are considered to have not fully achieved educational goals optimally. Compared to developed countries such as Singapore, Japan, and South Korea, Indonesia is still far behind when talking about curriculum, especially in terms of policy consistency, material relevance, and readiness to face the needs of 21st-century learning. Therefore, a more comprehensive curriculum reform is needed so that Indonesia can improve the quality of education and approach the educational success standards of Asian countries that have previously achieved significant results(Haryanti & Karim, 2024). And among the many schools in Indonesia, Vocational High Schools (SMK) have a unique advantage in improving the quality of education because they not only teach theory, but also equip students with real skills that can be directly used in the world of work. In SMK, students are encouraged to try various new things directly, starting from industrial internships, making projects, to learning to build their own businesses such as online business or drop shipping systems. This approach makes students more confident, more independent, and more ready to face the needs of the modern world that continues to change. That is why SMK is often considered a place capable of producing young generations who are creative, skilled, and not only ready to work but also ready to create new job opportunities(Qurbani et al., 2020).

Especially in SMKs with informatics majors, they have many advantages because they are able to prepare students not only theoretically, but also with practical skills that match the needs of the digital industry, such as the ability to design information systems, model system architecture, and also apply software design methodologies. So that students graduate with real skills to directly enter the workforce or continue to higher education in the IT field(Sumantika et al., 2024). And in many SMKs, especially those majoring in informatics, learning using the PjBL model or method provides opportunities for students to learn collaboratively, meaning they do not only receive theory in class, but also work on real projects, complete tasks with peers, and apply the concepts learned through practice. The implementation of differentiated PjBL in informatics classes shows that this method significantly increases students' collaboration skills compared to other conventional methods. This is because PjBL requires students to be active, communicate, discuss, and share responsibility in completing projects, so that besides academic aspects, students also develop social and teamwork skills, which are among the many important abilities in the world of work and industry(Fadillah, 2024).

In the implementation of the PjBL method, it is also very important to conduct several evaluations of the effectiveness of project-based learning. This evaluation can help assess how far this model or method is able to develop or improve students' creativity, and student learning outcomes are also often used as a benchmark to assess how effective the learning process in the classroom is. The learning outcomes achieved by students certainly do not stand alone, but are also influenced by various interrelated factors, both from the school environment and from the students themselves. To obtain more optimal learning outcomes, a learning method is needed that can facilitate the development of students' abilities. Through project-based learning methods, students do not only collect information, but also have the opportunity to develop new skills gradually until they are able to produce a certain product or prototype(Umar, 2018). And in the context of informatics learning, it is very important to see how the implementation of project-based learning can affect students' performance. Through tasks taken from real situations, students are also required to think creatively, work together with peers, and solve problems systematically, all of which are part of the main characteristics of project-based learning. With the implementation of this approach, it is hoped that students' learning outcomes in each informatics subject can improve(Roring et al., 2023).

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Learning in vocational high schools (SMK) today is still very much teacher-centered, so students do not yet have sufficient opportunities to create or be creative and to develop broader ways of thinking, or it can be said that many schools still apply teacher-centered learning. Meanwhile, the world of work and the demands of the 21st century require graduates who are able to think creatively, work collaboratively, and solve problems effectively. When the learning process is too passive, students become less engaged and are not accustomed to facing real situations that require initiative. Therefore, it is important to implement the Project Based Learning (PjBL) method, which allows students to learn through projects, work in teams, and find solutions to real problems. With this approach, learning in vocational high schools can become more lively and relevant, while greatly helping students build the skills they truly need in the future.

RESEARCH METHOD

The Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method is one way of research that organizes the process of searching and reviewing literature neatly and systematically. Through clear steps, starting from determining the focus of the questions, selecting sources that are truly relevant, to assessing and summarizing previous research findings. SLR also greatly helps researchers see the bigger picture of the topic being studied. With this systematic approach, researchers can understand the development of existing studies, find certain patterns or trends, and identify parts that are still rarely discussed. This process makes the review results more reliable and provides a strong foundation for subsequent research(Triandini et al., 2019). This literature review uses articles that discuss project-based learning models or methods (Project Based Learning), creative thinking skills, and student learning outcomes. The articles used come from publications from

1997 to 2025. The data collection process is carried out by documenting articles that have similar topics, then analyzed descriptively to observe trends and important findings from each study. All analysis results are presented in the form of summaries to make them easier to understand. Source searches were carried out using Google Scholar with keywords: Project Based Learning, creative thinking, vocational informatics students, and learning outcomes. Articles that did not fall under these keywords were not included as review material. The main focus of this review is research that truly examines the implementation of PjBL in vocational informatics programs within the period of 1997 to 2025.

In this review, the aim is to take a closer look at how Project Based Learning can help develop critical thinking skills in vocational students. The main focus is on what is actually produced by the implementation of PjBL, namely the increase in students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and solve problems. This study also highlights who is involved, namely vocational students, especially those majoring in informatics, who are indeed required to have higher-order thinking skills. This review describes where the implementation of PjBL takes place, namely in vocational classes that apply project-based learning in productive subjects. From a time perspective, the review highlights when PjBL is used, namely during the learning process that is adjusted to the stages of project completion. This study also explains why PjBL is chosen, because this method provides opportunities for students to be directly involved, explore ideas, and make decisions while completing the project. As for how PjBL helps improve critical thinking, it can be seen from students' activities when they identify real problems, search for supporting information, design solutions, and evaluate the final results of their work. Through this process, students' critical thinking skills develop more naturally and meaningfully.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

No	Project Based Learning Syntax	Activities	Creativity Point
1.	Determining the Essential Question	Teachers and students determine real problems or challenges that are relevant to the Informatics expertise competencies, such as creating a simple application, designing UI/UX, or developing a small system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring multiple possibilities to meet user needs • Defining innovative goals and project concepts
2.	Project Planning	Students design a work plan, divide team tasks, determine the software to use (such as Figma, Android Studio, Visual Studio Code), and create a project timeline.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing creative strategies and approaches • Brainstorming various solution concepts • Choosing the most creative and feasible ideas

3.	Scheduling	Teachers and students create activity schedules such as brainstorming, coding, testing, revision, and presentation stages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuring creative workflows • Planning time for experimentation • Adjusting ideas when obstacles arise
4.	Project Implementation	Students begin developing the project (designing UI, programming, debugging). Teachers monitor, guide, and conduct weekly checkpoints.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimenting with designs and features • Modifying ideas during development • Producing original work through iterative creation
5.	Monitoring	Students test the application or product, identify bugs, fix errors, and ensure it meets user needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refining ideas to improve product quality • Enhancing creativity through revisions • Developing better versions based on feedback
6.	Product presentation	Students present their projects to the class or guest teachers from industry, showcasing demos of the applications or systems they built.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expressing creative choices clearly • Showcasing unique design or system features • Reflecting creativity through storytelling and demonstrations
7.	Reflection	Students write reflections or conduct group discussions about the process, challenges, solutions, and improvements for future projects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluating creative growth • Generating new ideas for future projects • Identifying personal creative strengths and weaknesses

Because learning in vocational high schools (SMK) today is still very much centered on the teacher, one solution that can be done to overcome teacher-centered learning in SMKs is to start implementing the Project Based Learning (PjBL) method. Through this approach, students not only listen to explanations, but directly engage in working on projects that are close to real-world situations and in accordance with their vocational competencies. The process of working in teams, searching for ideas, solving problems, and producing products makes students more active, creative, and accustomed to thinking critically. On the other hand, the teacher acts as a companion who guides and gives direction, no longer being the only source of information. In this way, the learning atmosphere becomes more lively and relevant, while also helping students build the skills they truly need to face the world of work and the challenges of the 21st century (Eliza et al., 2019). And for the creativity of Informatics SMK students, it can be improved by applying the Project Based Learning (PJBL) method, because through real projects they can directly experiment in the real world, as well as try new ideas, and find the best ways to solve problems. When students

design, create, and present their projects, starting from simple applications, interface designs, to small systems that they build themselves. They are naturally encouraged to think more flexibly, critically, and originally. Learning also becomes more lively and feels more relevant, because what they work on is similar to the challenges they will encounter in the working world. Besides helping students become more creative, the PJBL approach also strengthens teamwork skills, communication, and even builds a portfolio that they can use to apply for jobs later. In other words, PJBL not only makes students more creative, but also more prepared to face the continuously growing digital industry. (Suantara et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

From the overall discussion, it can be concluded that project-based learning (Project Based Learning/PjBL) has a very significant impact in helping vocational high school (SMK) students, especially those in the informatics major, become more creative and ready to face the demands of an increasingly developing era. This method provides space for students to learn actively through real project activities, work with their peers, and find solutions to the problems they encounter. This learning experience has proven capable of fostering creativity, increasing critical thinking skills, and also making students more confident in practicing what they have learned. The literature review also shows that education in Indonesia still needs to catch up with other Asian countries that have more advanced education systems. However, SMK has its own advantage because it is able to connect theory with practice directly, especially in the informatics major, which becomes even stronger because students have the opportunity to learn skills that are truly needed in the digital industry. With the support of learning models such as PjBL, the learning process becomes more relevant, interesting, and meaningful for students. Overall, research from 1997 to 2025 reinforces that PjBL not only increases creativity but also has a positive impact on learning outcomes, motivation, and students' career readiness. Therefore, this method is very suitable to continue being used and developed in SMKs, especially in informatics programs, so that graduates produced are truly ready to compete and contribute in an ever-developing technological era.

In addition, this review shows that the success of implementing PjBL greatly depends on the role of the teacher as a mentor who is able to guide students without limiting their creativity. When teachers act as facilitators, the learning atmosphere becomes more open and provides space for students to try, ask questions, and explore various ideas. This approach also makes the learning process feel closer to the real world, so that students can more easily understand the material and find the best ways to solve the problems they face. In other words, student-centered learning through PjBL has proven to be more effective than traditional methods that only focus on teacher explanations.

Besides giving an impact on academic abilities, the implementation of PjBL also helps students develop important skills such as communication, teamwork, time management, and responsibility. All these skills are highly needed by SMK students, especially those in the informatics major, so that they are ready to compete in the constantly changing digital industry. With the increased creativity, critical thinking skills, and students' career readiness, PjBL becomes a learning method that is not only relevant but also very important to continue applying and

developing. In this way, SMKs can truly produce graduates who are skilled, confident, and ready to face the challenges of the future working world.

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